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ANALYSIS OF FOUR WAVE MIXING IN OPTICAL FIBER

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Abstract:

The four wave mixing effect on bit error rate, Q -factor, output spectrums and eye diagrams at different channel spacing is investigated. The design, implementation and performance analysis of four wave mixing in optical communication system for different values of spacing between input channels has been done. In this paper investigation of four wave mixing effect with different number of channels at various channel spacing has also been done. All the input channels are spaced evenly at various values like 5.25 GHz, 9 GHz, 19GHz, 24 GHz, 39 GHz, 49 GHz, 59GHz, 74GHz with the different number of channels at the input i.e. with 2, 4, 6, 8, 12, 14, 16, 18 input channels. the comparison of four wave mixing effect at various values of channel spacing. According to results, spacing of 74 GHz has the lowest BER and better system performance. Hence, the higher spacing values between the input channels is recommended for long distance transmission without four wave mixing. Analyzing the effect of four wave mixing for each channel spacing with these number of channels in terms of eye diagrams, BER, eye opening and Q -factor.

Keywords: Four-wave mixing (FWM), Dense Wave Division Multiplexing (DWDM)

1. INTRODUCTION

Non-linear effects in optical fiber have become a most recent area of academic research area of academic research in optical fiber based on DWDM system. when launch power in optical fiber is high man a set value known as threshold value than transmission is limited by Non linear effects. on Linear effects in Optical fibers depends on the refractive index of the optical medium and the intensity of light. One of the well-known non-linear effects in Optical fibers is the Four-wave mixing (FWM) phenomenon. This paper discusses the effect of channel spacing, laser power, and dispersion, length of the optical fiber and the variation of input power to compensate the effect of FWM when implemented in a short haul environment. When a high-power optical signal is launched into an optical fiber, the linearity of the optical response is lost due to the dependence of the medium's refractive index on the intensity of light in the medium. One such nonlinear effect, which is due to the third-order electric susceptibility, is called the optical Kerr effect. Four-wave mixing (FWM) is a type of optical Kerr effect [1], [2] and occurs when light of two or more different wavelengths is launched into an optical fiber. FWM involve nonlinear interaction among four optical waves and is referred to as third order parametric process because it is caused by the third order nonlinear susceptibility. The nonlinear effects degrade the system performance like by introducing interference, distortion excess attenuation of the optical signals.

II: FOUR-WAVE MIXING (FWM)

The major source of non-linear crosstalk for DWDM light wave system is FWM (four wave mixing). when three wave of frequencies $\omega_i, \omega_j, \omega_k$ co-propagates inside the fiber FWM can generate new wave at the frequencies

$$\omega_f = \omega_i + \omega_j + \omega_k$$

For an N-channel system I, j, k vary from 1 to N, resulting in large combination of new frequency generated by FWM [3, 4]. In FWM, power of main frequency is reduced due to generation of new frequency. System performance is affected by loss in channel power of new frequency. FWM effect occur when the phase matching condition is satisfied as particular combinations of fiber dispersion and signal frequencies. The FWM is a very

unpleasant transmission phenomenon occurring in a transparent optical network based on Dense Wave Division Multiplexing(DWDM)[5], but it could be used advantageously for implementing optical devices such as wavelength converters, parametric amplifiers, optical de-multiplexers, chromatic dispersion compensators, as well as signal to noise regenerators.

III: SIMULATION SETUP

The simulation setup for showing the effect of changing spacing between the input channels on four wave mixing .The continuous wave laser (L1-L8) is used to create the carrier signal. In this setup, eight users are taken in account whose wavelengths have a specific difference i.e. spacing between them. The frequency of first user is kept at 191.97 nm. The wavelengths of next users is set as per the spacing requirement i.e. at wavelength difference of 5.25 GHz, 9 GHz, 19 GHz, 24 GHz, 74 GHz. The data source (ds1-ds8) is used to generate the random input data bit sequence at the rate of 9 Gbps[3].

The light signal modulates the input data. The modulator (m1-m8) is driven by the modulator driver (d1-d8) which decides the input data format. The input data format used here is NRZ raised cosine[6]. The modulated data from all the users is combined using a combiner (c1). The post amplifier (a1) amplifies the signal before allowing it to enter into the fiber to avoid losses. Then this signal is sent over the fiber (f1) of length 100 Km. All the attenuation, dispersion and non linear effects are activated. The in-line amplifier (a2) amplifies the signal in the transmission medium itself. Then the signal is again passed through a fiber (f2) of length 100 Km. Then pre-amplifier (a3) is used to amplify the signal before allowing it to enter into the receiver section. After amplification, the signal reaches the receiver. At the receiver, the signal is demultiplexer by using a splitter (s1) which splits this signal into the same number of signals as were transmitted. The photodiode (p1) is used for optical to electrical conversion. Then the signal is passed through the Bessel filter (Lf1) which is made to work as low pass filters and the final output signal is received. An optical scope (probe1) is attached at the output of combiner to examine the input signal. Another optical scope (probe2) is placed at the output of splitter to examine the four wave mixing effect in frequency spectrum. An electrical scope (scope3) is kept at the receiver output to examine the eye diagram, BER, Q-factor. Some optical scopes are placed in the intermediate stages to analyze the output.

Simulation Model: The system is divided into three major section transmitter, channel(optical fiber)and receiver. Transmitter consist of pseudo random bit sequence Non-return to zero codes, continuous wave laser, Mach lander modulation for fwm

Fig 1: Simulation Setup

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In fig.2 the four wave mixing effect is clearly seen in the above output spectrum for 5.25 GHz spacing as unnecessary peaks at various frequencies are occurring at the sides of the input spectrum. Moreover, the peaks at the input frequencies have also diminished due to four wave mixing occurred after crossing the non linear fiber.

Fig. 2. Input optical spectrum used for analyzing 5.25 GHz channel spacing in FWM.

Fig. 3. Represents the output spectrum for the various values of spacing between the input users using the channel spacing of 9GHz in FWM.

FWM at channel spacing of 9GHz

Fig. 3. Effect of four wave mixing at 19 GHz channel spacing

Fig.4. Input optical spectrum used for analyzing 19 FWM effect

Fig. 5. Input optical spectrum for the channel spacing of 24GHz FWM effect it is clear that changing the modulator drivers least effect the four wave mixing occurring in the communication channel. NRZ

Fig. 6. Input optical spectrum for the channel spacing of 74GHz FWM effect

The above spectrums shows that as the spacing between the input channels/users increases, the four wave mixing effect goes on decreasing. The unwanted peaks are maximum when the spacing is 5.25 GHz and are minimum when the spacing is 74 GHz. This shows that lesser the spacing between different input users/channels, more is the interference between the input frequencies i.e. more is the four wave mixing effect. On increasing the spacing between the input channels, the four wave mixing decreases.

Fig:7: Channel spacing in GHz

Fig:7 Shows the variation of BER on the basis of spacing between the input channels. The figure shows that BER goes on decreasing with the increasing spacing. It shows that the interference between the input frequencies and hence the four wave mixing effect decreases with the increasing channel spacing.

Fig.8. shows the variation of Q-factor with the spacing between the input channels.

Fig. 8. shows the variation of Q-factor with the spacing between the input channels. The graph shows that the Q-factor increases on increasing the channel spacing. It is maximum when the channel spacing is 80 GHz and is minimum when the channel spacing is 5.25 GHz

Fig. 9. Represent the variation of eye opening with the channel spacing. The graph shows that eye opening decreases on increasing the spacing between the input channels.

Fig.10.Represents the variation of eye opening with the channel spacing

Fig.11.shows the eye diagram for 74Hz spacing The eye diagrams show that the eye diagram clarity goes on increasing with the increasing spacing between the input channels.

V.CONCLUSION

In this chapter, the design, implementation and performance analysis of four wave mixing in optical communication system for different values of spacing between input channels is presented. The comparison of four wave mixing effect at various values of channel spacing revealed that 74 GHz spacing has the edge over 5.25 GHz spacing in optical communication system. It is found that spacing of 74 GHz has the lowest BER and

better system performance. Hence, the higher spacing values between the input channels is recommended for long distance transmission without four wave mixing. It can be seen from the graphs of BER, Q-factor and eye opening that higher channel spacing gives the best performance as compared to lower channel spacing. Hence, it is concluded that higher channel spacing is best suitable to be employed in the optical communication systems minimizing the four wave mixing effect. It has been observed that on increasing the number of input channels/users, the interference increases and thus, the four wave mixing effect also increases. The eye opening decreases as the number of channels increases. Increasing the number of channels causes the Q-factor to decrease.

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